

IMPLEMENTING GOOD FAITH PRINCIPLE BETWEEN DMS PROGROWERS LTD AND TANGAN PERTOLONGAN BALI FOUNDATION: ASSESSING THEIR LEGAL OBLIGATIONS

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Abstract:

Globalisation is pushing all countries to unlock the border and let foreign elements enter their countries. This theoretical paper attempts to strengthen the accountability aspect of normative stakeholder theory with a more robust notion of stakeholder engagement derived from the concept of good faith. The contract's connection is wrapped out in the contract and could be placed as an international contract if the parties come from different countries. As an international contract, there is a variety of terms and conditions that would be applied to make sure that all parties understand clearly their rights and obligations. One of the engagements is the relationship between DMS Progrowers Ltd as the company subject to New Zealand law, and Tangan Pertolongan Bali subject to Indonesian law. Both parties are freely binded to the Recognised Seasonal Employment New Zealand program. The type of contract between the parties is arranged by Memorandum of Understanding (MoU). The MoU is familiar with the common law system but not the Europa Continental system adopted by Indonesian Law. The results show that good faith is the most critical element for parties entering the contract. Even though the parties ruled under a different system of law, they honoured and respected each other. The challenge of parties is how they build trust with the other, where there is no single article that mentions the legal consequences if one party did not perform the obligation. Furthermore, the need of good spirit and good faith comes naturally from both parties.

Keywords: Contract; Good Faith; Legal Systems

1. INTRODUCTION

The freedom of contract is a common principle that applying in the international activities. The parties entering the contract with the mutual benefit as its purpose. Both of them are expecting to contribute and also supporting one each other. There are several types of contracts that are known in the business activities. The parties then spells out the provisions in detail in order to create certainty (Yee, 2001). The international activities always involve a foreign party as one of the parties and therefore the arrangements of contract need to be considered carefully.

One of the international business activities is the placement of Indonesian workers abroad. Before the arrangement of the work agreement is carried out, it is necessary to identify the parties who involve in the program. With the involvement of foreign parties in the formulation, drafting and signing the contracts, then this activity will automatically be drawn into the area of international business contracts (Hutagalung, 2013). Basically, there are some elements need to be considered by the parties as the part of preparation of contract. One of them, every single

promise contained in the agreement is made with valuable consideration (Aryan & Mirabbasi, 2016).

As mentioned in the beginning, the research is trying to identify the background of the parties and also their purposes to enter into the agreement. There are two parties who involve in the program of Recognised Seasonal Employer and they are Direct Management Services Pro Growers Ltd which based in New Zealand and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation which based in Bali, Indonesia. The different backgrounds of the parties will certainly affect their style and habits in contracting. However, it is not an obstacle for both parties to continue to cooperate.

Instead using the contract in this business relationship, the parties are prefer to place their interest into Memorandum of Understanding. In the Indonesian legal system, the use of MoU in a relationship tends to be difficult to find. Most cooperative relationships are contained in the agreement. This fact is interesting so that it needs to be studied further about the process of implementing this relationship. Based on the explanation above, there are several questions arise that need to be explored further. The first, how is the principle of good faith from both parties applied in the MoU between DMS Pro Growers Ltd and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation? Second, what are the consequences for parties who do not perform their legal obligations? Third, what is the regulation will be applied in the MoU between DMS Pro Growers Ltd and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation?

The research aims to find out the factors that influence the parties to perform the good faith principle in the MoU. Another purpose of this research is to see the impact for the parties if one of them not perform the obligation. The last result that expected from the research is to analyse the type of regulation would be applied in the MoU. There was a research have been done that related with this research but both have different perspective and the approach. However, the current research is focusing in the relationship between the facilitators, they are Direct Management Services Pro Growers Now Zealand and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation.

2. METHOD

The type of research in this research is normative research conducted based on secondary data or literature. However, this research is also supported by data obtained through interviews with parties who have experience and knowledge that related to the topics raised. Data were analyzed with descriptive qualitative analysis with content analysis.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The principle of good faith from both parties that applied in the MoU between DMS Pro Growers Ltd and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation

Recognised Seasonal Employer (RSE) is the program that owned by New Zealand government. It is created as the solution for the business actors who related with the grapes, apples and kiwi fruit industry. New Zealand government produce the policy so that the people from overseas

able to come and work in New Zealand. One of the company which join the RSE is Direct Management Services Pro Growers Ltd (DMS). DMS has two big pack houses that located at Te Puke and Te Puna as the part of Bay of Plenty area at North Island of New Zealand. DMS Pro Growers Ltd concerning at the kiwi fruits packaging and also store them before export.

The RSE program was designed to support the countries that located nearby New Zealand such as Samoa, Fiji, Vanuatu and Tonga. New Zealand government is using the RSE program not only to solve the problem of minimum number of workers in New Zealand but in the same time they are wish to support their neighbour countries as the part of development program. Indonesian as the country that located far from New Zealand can be the part of RSE because several company of pack houses are already recruited the workers from Indonesia before the RSE program resulted.

The Indonesian workers have been employed since 2007 by the companies in New Zealand that focus in the kiwi fruit industry such as DMS, Satara, Seeka and East Pack. The companies are pleased with the performance of Indonesian workers and that fact can be onservred by their commitment to continue the recruitment. The good experience in the past also create the opportunity for the companies to train and place the Indonesian workers in several position where they can receive a better rate wages. One of the consistent commitment is shown by DMS which employ the Indonesian workers until now. The high performance of Indonesian workers created the satisfaction for the company. The fact is followed by the increase of economy benefit for DMS.

There are some instruments required to protect and arrange the rights obligations of parties who invlove in the RSE program. The parties who bring contribution in RSE program are:

- a. DMS Pro Growers Ltd.
- b. Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation
- c. Bali Duta Mandiri
- d. Indonesian government
- e. New Zealand government
- f. The Indonesian workers

In the beginning, the partnership is initiated by DMS Pro Growers and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation. The rights and obligations of parties are regulated in the Memorandum on Understanding (MoU). The structure of MoU of partnership as below:

- a. The name of MoU. The head of agreement is mentioned at the top of MoU.
- b. The parties. There are two parties who written in the MoU, they are DMS Pro Growers Ltd and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation.
- c. Background. In this part, the parties is describing about their background of activity, the location or domicile and their intends. The parties also mentioning the legal standing or permit related to running the partnership.

- d. Terms. Terms consist of the date of MoU would be applied, services that provided by the Foundation and the charges that would be paid by DMS.
- e. The Obligation of parties. There are some specific and detail of requirements which mentioned in this part. It is regulating the mechanism and technically how the program would be done from beginning until finish.
- f. Termination. The parties arrange the mechanism of reporting one each other if any of party defaults the obligations in the MoU.
- g. Reporting. This provision is arrange the communication between the parties regarding to all circumstances.
- h. Confidentiality. The private information is arranged as well to avoid the unexpected party who use the information for wrong purpose.
- i. Legal Costs. These term is pointing the parties who responsible to cover the legal cost of preparation and implementation of MoU.
- j. Counterpart Execution. It is the statement of effective date of implementation of MoU.

The interdependence of parties is the most important factor for the success of MoU where it becomes the strong relationship between them. The one party would treat the other party with high respect and honour. It is not guarantee for all parties would perform their obligation but each parties should respect the other by showing the will to obedience (Hobbes, 1952).

The understanding of parties will become deeper as the relationship lasts and it is a natural where the experience in the past will speak a lot about the other party (Paramita, 2020). Even in some contract practices, one party can act more, then what is specified in the contract. It is called performing beyond the expectation as same as what Jesus Christ explained in the Bible, Book of Matthew Chapter 5, and verse 41 “And whosoever shall compel thee to go a mile, go with him twain.

The way to respect the other party would be applied by serving the other with the best standard. Instead to think how to get the benefit from other, the parties would busy to try helping and blessing one each other. Those similar understanding will create the trust and confidence where they are the part of good faith principle. The example of manifestation of good faith principle implementation in the MoU between DMS and Foundation is in the monitoring program. The Foundation has an obligation to do the monitoring of workers who work under RSE program at DMS every year and based on the MoU then DMS is only responsible to provide one way ticket form Indonesia to Bali where the return must be covered by the Foundation. But in fact, DMS does beyond the obligation by providing the arrival and return ticket for the Foundation.

Manifestation of good faith principle by the parties can be observed through their commitment in competing to giving the best to another party. Instead focusing to the action of other party, the parties are trying to find the way to contribute in other party interest. By implementing these attitude, the parties will have no time to be selfish and advance their interest.

Blackburn and friends describe more detail about the principle of offer and acceptance. This principle are known well in business practical in the common law system (Blackburn et al, 1988). They said that “an acceptance consists of words or actions by which an offeree signifies his or her intention to be bound by the offer”. Sometime, what happens in a relationship is not just something that is expected but something that is not expected. The problem can happen and will create an impact to the parties. It is not a few the relationship could be ends in a way that is not wise. The important key for the parties to face the problem is communication (Vlahna & Kuçi, 2022). The intensive communication need to be done by transparency so that the parties could find the solution for all problems in their relationship. It is an critical factor which determine the success of relationship.

The MoU between DMS and Foundation realize that the communication as a prior and arrange it in the MoU. The technology is help a lot for the parties to communicate where both of them able to it by e-mail and other media do. The long distance and different time are not an obstruction for them. The parties hoping that their communication is able to identify the small potential problem and solve it as soon as possible. They are able to listen different perspective from different approach and background. At the end of the day, both parties would achieve their own success.

3.2. The consequences for parties who do not perform their legal obligations

The language factor is an important element for the success in a business and it is a challenge for DMS which employ the workers who have a different language (Bartley et la, 2016). Based on that fact, the Foundation agree to place some leaders of workers to facilitate the communication from time to time so that all information can be delivered completely. The leaders of workers also supervise and monitor the workers able to execute all instruction that given to them.

Long before the letter of offer is given, DMS first applies for an Agreement To Recruit (ATR) to Immigration Department of New Zealand. It would take time for the Immigration New Zealand to process the application. The Immigration of New Zealand would examine and analyse the application and then give the approval once it complete.

The ATR that released by Immigration New Zealand has the code of application number and also Client Number at the top of letter. It means these ATR is specifically given to the only one company and cannot be used or changed to other companies. Immigration New Zealand would provide the unique ATR number for the approval. The number is very important where it would be used for all workers when they fill the form of Visa application. Next steps, DMS is allow to recruit the workers from overseas where the name of countries are mentioned in the ATR letter.

The background and objectives of RSE is also declared in the ATR where it allow horticulture and viticulture business to supplement their New Zealand workforce with non-New Zealand citizen or residence class visa holder workers when labour demand exceeds the available New Zealand workforce and employers have made reasonable attempts to train and recruit New Zealand citizens and residence class visa holder. The deduction and rate information are also

arranged in the ATR for the policy that applied by New Zealand government. This fact is confirmed the fact where the workers set their sight on the country such as New Zealand so that they able to make a better life (Santoso, 2014). New Zealand is one of the leading country in 20th rank as released by the World Bank in 2013.

There are 2 (two) sides of activity of preparation RSE program, the first is in Indonesia side and the second is in New Zealand side. Both parties taking their own parts to perform their obligations. As the guideline for both parties, DMS and Foundation are set up the time line and action plan. The document arrangement process in the RSE program is quite long and involves many parties and agencies in Indonesia and New Zealand. It is very important for all parties understand and perform their parts and contribute in time. Therefore they need the timeline that explain details activities, personal in charge and also the schedule.

As mentioned above that there are 2 sides activities in preparation of documents, they are Indonesia side and New Zealand side. There are some activities in Indonesia and New Zealand that need to be arranged, as below:

- a. **Identification and Selection.** In the beginning the Foundation sets up the criteria for candidates of RSE program participants. The criteria is helping the Foundation to do the identification and offer the program to participants. The next step is selection step where the process is fully controlled by internal Foundation.
- b. **Medical Check-Up and X-Ray.** Immigration New Zealand is giving fully attention for all people who enter the country. One of the aspects is the health issue, therefore DMS and Foundation are concern with all participants healthy condition. It is not all public hospital that recognized by Immigration New Zealand so that is why the medical check-up for the participants is only arranged by the hospital that have a cooperation with New Zealand government. The good attitude and good health are the important key for the workers and company (Trisnawati et al, 2015).
- c. **Passport Arrangement.** Passport is a document that released by government as a document for person who want to travel and enter another country. The workers from Indonesia are required to have passport so that they able to leave Indonesia and enter New Zealand.
- d. **Good Conduct Letter.** Due the international criminal issue, New Zealand government require all workers from overseas who want to enter the country shall provide the good conduct letter. The letter would attach in the same time when the workers apply for the Visa.
- e. **Recommendation from Manpower Department of Indonesia.** The recommendation is a legal document that released by Indonesian government as the part of legal protection that given to the workers. It is the way from Indonesian government to do monitor and evaluation of program where they analyse for the number of workers, the type of job and also the rate of wages. The tight procedure is applied by Indonesia government to avoid

the human trafficking, slavery and physical abuse where they are quite often in the sector of maid or house helper (Nuraeny, 2018).

- f. **Justice of Peace Legalization.** The activity is arranged in New Zealand where all documents need to be stamps or notarized before they submitted to Indonesian embassy for endorsement.
- g. **Indonesian Embassy Endorsement.** All documents that already stamps by Justice of Peace would deliver to Indonesian Embassy for endorsement. Normally, the Indonesia embassy would do verification of documents by contact the company in New Zealand and if needed they would do visitation to the site. Once everything confirmed then Indonesian Embassy endorse all documents.
- h. **Recruitment Letter Arrangement.** Foundation then collaborate with one of PPTKIS (Pelaksana Penempatan Tenaga Kerja Indonesia Swasta). It is the company, which given written permit from Indonesian government as a company to arrange the service and placement of Indonesian workers abroad. The company would apply the recruitment letter from Manpower Department as a legal procedure for Indonesian workers (Wicaksono et al, 2018). There are some regulation that implemented by Indonesia government and establish the institutions to as an active action to support the prevention and law enforcement in legal protection for Indonesian workers so that they would have fairness.
- i. **Visa Arrangement.** The form of Visa application need to be filled carefully and detail. The form and the payment of Visa application would be done at New Zealand visa application center (VFS Global). Normally, it would take 10 working days to get Visa since the form submitted.
- j. **Pre Departure Training.** Pre Departure Training must be done as the requirement by Indonesian regulation. The purpose of training is to equip the workers for working overseas. There are some information would be delivered in the training by different trainer who come from different institution and background. The subjects are the rights and obligation of workers, the culture of country where the workers would be placed, the company and job description and the info related.

The activities that described above as the obligations for parties, therefore they need to fully responsible. In fact, there are so many activities in the process but all activities are connected one each other. The fail of one activity would give the implication to the next or other activities. In the same meanings, if one of activities cannot be done then it will cause the failure to other activities or even the failure of program.

The experience in the past is telling the parties to keep a good communication by updating one each other regarding with the progress of every single arrangement. The good communication makes the parties able to detect the potential problem and then trying to solve it together. Instead creating the argumentation and conflict, the parties are prefer to keep on focusing to find the solution by implementing different way and plan.

The failure of one party to perform then it would create the loss for themselves and that is why all parties would try their best to fulfil their obligations. The MoU between DMS and Foundation does not rule details about the legal consequences if any party fail to perform their parts. Both parties have a similar understanding where one of party terminate the MoU then it would become the normal condition as same as the MoU not exist.

3.3. The regulation will be applied in the MoU between DMS Pro Growers Ltd and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation

The principle of contract in New Zealand that inspired by Common Law system has a characteristic of offer and acceptance concept. The details of those concepts could be found in a legal guide for the legal and business community that released by Legal Commission of New Zealand at Wellington on October 1998. In the article number 50 arrange the basic principles where in order to prove a binding contract formed under New Zealand law.

The bargaining theory by Richard A. Posner define the theory as a form of expedience in receiving or the effort to create equal position in order to find the same purpose so that can achieve fair consensus. Posner pointed that reciprocal promise as the important element in the process of bargaining (Sugianto, 2013). The principle of freedom of contract inspirit the law as an umbrella for all agreement where in Indonesia this principle is ruled in the Chapter 1338 verse 1 of Kitab Undang-Undang Hukum Perdata and at the end it will determine implementation of an agreement that create the balance and fairness for both parties (Suharnoko, 2012).

The agreement also require the legal certainty for all parties. MoU between DMS and Foundation is arranged two parties who come from different country and different system of law. Both parties are hoping that there will be no legal conflict during the period of contract. The MoU between DMS and Foundation does not mention clearly the choosing of law or which law would be applied to solve any dispute that could be happened in the future. Although, both parties are trusting one each other, but the legal guidance and declaration of choosing law are needed. The purpose of ruling the choosing of law is bring legal certainty to the MoU.

4. IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The principle of good faith from both parties that applied in the MoU between DMS Pro Growers Ltd and Tangan Pertolongan Bali Foundation could be seen from the action and attitude of parties to honour and respect one other. Good communication is an important key to the success of the implementation of the good faith principle. Performing beyond expectation is a characteristic of respecting and honouring. The MoU between DMS and Foundation has no legal consequences if one party does not perform the legal obligation. It will become the normal condition if one of party terminates the MoU. However, the parties consider respecting and honouring the other party as the implementation of good faith to avoid the loss for themselves. Hence, the MoU between DMS and Foundation does not rule out the type of regulation and choice of law. It happened as the experience in the past where the parties never

had a conflict between them. However, the regulation of choice of law is needed to bring legal certainty for the parties.

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DECLARATION OF INTEREST

Authors declare there are no competing interests in this research and publication.

References

- Aryan, S., & Mirabbasi, B. (2016). The Good Faith Principle and Its Consequences in Pre-Contractual Period: A Comparative Study on English and French Law. *J. Pol. & L.*, 9, 232.
- Bartley, A., Beddoe, L., Duke, J., Fouché, C., Harington, P., & Shah, R. (2016). Crossing borders: key features of migrant social workers in New Zealand. *Aotearoa New Zealand Social Work*, 23(3), 16-30.
- Blackburn J.D., et al. (1988), *The Legal Environment Of Business*, Richard D. Irwin Inc., United States of America.
- Dawkins, C. E. (2014). The principle of good faith: Toward substantive stakeholder engagement. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 121(2), 283-295.
- Hobbes, T. (1952), *Leviathan, Or, Matter, Form, and Power of Commonwealth Ecclesiastical and Civil*, William Benton Publisher, New York.
- Hutagalung, S.M. (2013), *Kontrak Bisnis di Asean*, Jakarta: Sinar Grafika.
- Nuraeny, H. (2018). Pengiriman tenaga kerja migran sebagai salah satu bentuk perbudakan modern dari tindak pidana perdagangan orang. *Jurnal Hukum dan Peradilan*, 4(3), 501-518.
- Paramita, K. (2020). Much in Little: The Umbrella Clause that Changes the International Investment Protection Standard. *Hasanuddin Law Review*, 6(1), 25-45. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.20956/halrev.v6i1.1570>
- Santoso, I. (2014), *Diaspora, Globalisme, Keamanan dan Keimigrasian*, Bandung: Pustaka Reka Cipta.
- Sugianto, F. (2013), *Economic Analysis of Law*, Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- Suharnoko, (2012). *Hukum Perjanjian Teori dan Analisa Kasus*, Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- Trisnawati, D., Astuti, P., & Astrika, L. (2015). Peran Pemerintah dalam Memberikan Perlindungan terhadap Tenaga Kerja Indonesia yang Bekerja di Luar Negeri (Studi pada Dinas Tenaga Kerja dan Transmigrasi Provinsi Jawa Tengah). *Journal of Politics and Government Studies*, 4(2), 131-145, p.6.
- Vlahna, K., & Kuçi, H. (2022). The Creation of the Right of Real Servitude: Derivative and Original Method Based on the Kosovo and Some European Countries. *Hasanuddin Law Review*, 8(2), 111-121. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.20956/halrev.v8i2.3614>
- Wicaksono, D. and Hartanto. (2018). *Perlindungan Hak Asasi Anak di Bawah Umur sebagai Korban Tindak Pidana Kesusilaan di Wilayah Hukum Polres Boyolali*. Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Muhammadiyah Surakarta.
- Yee, W. P. (2001). Protecting parties' reasonable expectations: A general principle of good faith. *Oxford University Commonwealth Law Journal*, 1(2), 195-229.